

FIGURE 2-1a
Sediment Core Sample Locations
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-1b
Sediment Core Sample Locations
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-1c
Sediment Core Sample Locations
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

At individual coring stations, sediment samples were collected from the entire sediment profile to a target depth of 6 feet into the native sediment deposits. Samples were collected using a 2-foot composite interval.

At coring stations located on previously sampled transects, sediment samples were collected from the native sediment only. Three samples were collected using a 2-foot composite interval, to a target depth of 6 feet into the native sediment deposits.

LEGEND

- Soft sediment
- Gowanus Creek native sediments

FIGURE 2-2
 Diagram of Sediment Core Sampling Scheme
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-3a
Surface Sediment Sample Locations
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-3b
Surface Sediment Sample Locations
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-3c
Surface Sediment Sample Locations
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-4
Reference Area Surface Sediment Sample Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-5a
Surface Water Sample Locations
Upper Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-5b
Surface Water Sample Locations
Middle Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-5c
Surface Water Sample Locations
Lower Canal
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-7
Gowanus Canal Fish and Shellfish Tissue
Sample Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-8
Reference Area Fish and Shellfish Tissue
Sample Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-9
Air Sample Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

USEPA Survey Outfall Number	Corresponding NYCDEP Outfall Number
GC-CF-N-002	RH-034
GC-CF-N-003	
GC-CF-N-004	
GC-CF-N-005	
Not Observed	RH-033
GC-CF-E-001	RH-038
GC-CF-E-002	
GC-CF-E-003	
GC-CF-E-004	
GC-CF-E-005	
GC-CF-E-006	
Not Observed	RH-037
Not Observed	RH-036
GC-CF-E-016	OH-005
GC-CF-E-065	OH-007
GC-CF-E-066	
GC-CF-E-067	
GC-CF-W-67	RH-035
GC-CF-W-68	
GC-CF-W-69	
GC-CF-W-70	
GC-CF-W-072	RH-031
GC-CF-E-072	OH-006

CSO outfalls designated by blue triangle were observed during pipe outfall survey and were assigned a sequential outfall number using survey nomenclature. CSO outfalls designated by gray triangle were not observed during pipe outfall survey and were therefore not assigned a sequential outfall number. CSO locations obtained from NYCDEP Shoreline Survey Program.

FIGURE 2-10
 Sampled CSO and Other Pipe Outfall Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-11
Groundwater Monitoring Well Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Legend

- SOFT SEDIMENT
- NATIVE SEDIMENT
- FILTER SAND
- BENTONITE CHIPS
- FILL
- WATER TABLE

Note

HORIZONTAL SCALE EXAGGERATED TO SHOW MONITORING WELL CONSTRUCTION DETAILS.

FIGURE 2-12
 Typical Nested Well Construction Detail
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-13
Groundwater – Surface Water Interaction Sampling Locations
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 2-14
 Groundwater – Surface Water Transducer and Staff Gauge Locations
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York